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Correlation between Self-Efficacy and Choice of Career among Colleges of Education Mathematics Students in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between self-efficacy and choice of career among Colleges of Education Mathematics students in Kano State, Nigeria. Three research questions with their corresponding hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study was one hundred thirty-two NCE I Mathematics student-teachers as at 2019/2020 session. All the NCE I student-teachers participated in the study. Mathematics Student-Teachers Self-Efficacy Scale (MSTSES), adapted from the work of Usher and Pajares (2009), was the instrument used for the study. MSTSES was valid and reliable with a Cronbach Alpha of 0.84. Apart from demographic information, the instrument consists of 20 items designed based on the four sources of self-efficacy. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. While the hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance and analyzed using Point-Biserial correlation and Pearson product moment correlation, based on the findings, it was concluded that student-teachers' self-efficacy was low, and there was no significant correlation between the student-teachers' self-efficacy and teaching careers. The study recommends that students' self-efficacy in Mathematics and a Mathematics teaching career should be considered before they were admitted into teacher education programs.

Keywords: Mathematics, Self-efficacy, Student-teachers, Mathematics Teaching Career.

Introduction

Despite the importance and numerous applications of Mathematics within and outside the context of science and technology, students-teachers have learning difficulties in the subject, which leads to low Mathematics ability and low self-efficacy among the students. Mathematics is the basic foundation for a good understanding of not only sciences and technologies but also social and management sciences. Unfortunately, an alarming rate of low achievement, negative attitude, anxiety, and poor skills and abilities among student-teachers has been observed. Mathematics in general is one of the most challenging subjects for almost every student in Nigeria. Many student-

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teachers in tertiary institutions or universities were admitted to study Mathematics as their last option, which was by necessity (Odiri 2020).

Student-teachers are teachers in training in either colleges of education or universities. Pre-service and in-service teachers are the two types of student-teachers. Pre-service student teachers are newly admitted into teacher training programs, and they have no teaching experience. While in-service teachers were already employed in the teaching system and re-admitted to further their study. This study referred to student-teachers that have no teaching experience and are newly admitted to pursue an NCE (National Certificate in Education) certificate in colleges of education. The colleges of education were among the teacher-training institutions responsible for training teachers (Awofala et al. 2020). The main purpose of the colleges of education is to produce non-graduate as well as well-grooming teachers that can teach in primary, junior, and some courses in senior secondary schools due to the insufficient number of Mathematics teachers (National Commission for Colleges of Education [NCCE] 2012). Unfortunately, looking at the student-teachers' results, one may wonder what they will teach as future teachers.

Self-efficacy theory is based on students' beliefs about their abilities to meet high levels of task difficulty in order to achieve specific goals (Bandura, 1994; Segarra, & Julià, 2022). "Belief is an individual's capability to organize and execute the course of action required to provide attainment," Bandura stated. Self-efficacy is the confidence or belief in an individual's capability to perform a given task successfully (Benaoni 2016). Self-efficacy is not a learned skill; it is concerned with students' beliefs about their abilities to mastermind and strategize skills, and abilities in challenging situations (Segarra & Julià, 2022).

Mathematics self-efficacy refers to students' beliefs and abilities regarding Mathematics as a subject (Kouli 2021). It is the student's assessment of what they are capable of doing mathematically. Ampofo (2019) stresses that students' self-efficacy in Mathematics indicates the students' competence and efficiency to perform mathematical tasks successfully, and Gao (2020) affirmed that student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics has a significant impact on their academic achievement. Self-efficacy defines students' emotional feelings, interest, and thinking toward their Mathematics learning (Prince 2017; Simamora et al., 2019).

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Existing literature indicates that students' self-efficacy in Mathematics is a serious issue that requires the attention of all educational stakeholders (Prince 2017; Xu & Qi 2019); otherwise, Mathematics education will collapse, as seen in Nigeria. Understanding self-efficacy and how it affects student learning and their problem-solving ability could enhance students' Mathematical ability, interest, self-esteem, academic achievement, and retention in Mathematics (Köseolu 2015; Recber et al., 2018; Ampofo 2019; Simamora et al., 2019; Gao 2020).

Implicating this theory into the current situation of teaching and learning Mathematics in Nigeria, it can be observed that the self-efficacy of Mathematics teachers in the country is very low because their success is assessed through their students' end results, while every year students achieve poorly in Mathematics national examinations. And research by Kouli (2021) revealed that the higher the Mathematics teachers' self-efficacy, the higher the students' academic achievement in Mathematics.

Linking the theory with mathematical ability, student-teachers' low Mathematics ability and skills are influenced by their lack of or low self-efficacy in Mathematics, which in turn affects their career as future Mathematics teachers. It has been noticed that there is a decline in student-teachers' mathematical ability, confidence, and academic achievement (Mman & Tudunkaya, 2019). Which is the result of low Mathematics self-efficacy among the student-teachers. Literature shows that there are four sources of self-efficacy (Usher & Pajares 2009): mastery experience, vicarious experience, social persuasion, and physiological and emotional state.

Mastery experience; some researchers called it performance experience because it deals with the students' performance or achievement in a certain mathematical task. Mastery experiences typically occur when students succeed or fail in a mathematical task; this allows students to determine their belief in their ability to perform better in their Mathematics courses (Kouli, 2021).

Vicarious experience typically refers to how students perceive the academic skills of career role models, teachers, parents, older students, or classmates (Usher & Pajares 2009). Students can develop Mathematics self-efficacy by seeing or observing someone who demonstrates Mathematics competency. Through vicarious experience, students learn from their relatives, which influences their self-efficacy beliefs (Gao 2020).

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Gao (2020) believes that social persuasion can affect mastery and vicarious experience as a source of self-efficacy. Students' interactions with others, such as parents, teachers, peers, and/or community members, influence their self-efficacy positively or negatively. Students with low self-efficacy in Mathematics can be affected through interaction with others that have a high level of Mathematics self-efficacy (Kouli 2021).

Physiological and emotional state is the fourth source of self-efficacy; when students physically and emotionally feel contented or satisfied with a given Mathematics task, this stimulates the students' self-efficacy toward the subject (Bandura 1994). Also, when students are upset psychologically with Mathematics anxiety, phobia, or pain while attempting to complete a mathematical task, this will stimulate the student's self-efficacy negatively.

Going by the reviewed literature, all four sources can affect student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics, as research has revealed (Peker 2016, Prince 2017, Reyes 2019, Kouli 2021). Mathematics teacher educators and researchers need to pay attention to student teachers' self-efficacy as they are the future Mathematics teachers. Also, Mathematics teacher educators need to be careful to display their passion for teaching and learning Mathematics as it relates to the student-teachers' self-efficacy in teaching the subject in the future.

Benaoui (2016) conducted a study on "The Impact of Self-Efficacy in Mathematics on Urban High School Graduates' Math Performance." The findings of the study showed that only two of the four sources of self-efficacy, performance experiences and physiological and emotional state, were found to be statistically significant factors that influence students' performance, while vicarious experiences and verbal persuasion were not significant. Unsal et al. (2016) conducted a study on "Analysis of Mathematics Teachers' Self-Efficacy Levels Concerning the Teaching Process." The study was conducted in Turkey during the second term of the 2015–2016 academic year. The researchers concluded that Mathematics teachers stated opinions on having high self-efficacy beliefs concerning the teaching process, and these opinions differed based on gender and year of service. Ampofo (2019) examined the relationship between pre-service teacher's perceived self-efficacy in teaching Mathematics and their achievement in Mathematics. A descriptive design was used for the study. The study's population was pre-service teachers, with a sample size of forty students from Kibi College of Education, 47.5% of whom were male and 52.5% of whom were female. Data was

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collected through a Mathematics self-efficacy scale (MSES) questionnaire and a Mathematics achievement test (MAT). The findings of the study showed a relationship between the pre-service teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and their achievement in Mathematics.

Hence, with the main goals of Mathematics educators being to improve students' mathematical ability, especially student-teachers, who will be the future Mathematics educators, this study aimed to investigate the influence of self-efficacy on student-teacher's careers in Mathematics teaching.

Statement of the Research Problem

In decade, most researches were conducted on Mathematics teachers' professionalism, content knowledge, and pedagogical skills, but little attention is given to aspects like self-efficacy and career choice that can directly or indirectly affect the effectiveness, efficiency, and sustainability of teaching and learning Mathematics, this become the basis of this study. Because the student-teachers' ability and beliefs stimulate their Mathematics learning and values, which allow the student-teachers to engage or not engage in the study of Mathematics.

Objectives of the Study

This research work was designed to attain the following objectives, i.e.,

1. Determine the level of student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics.
2. Find out the relationship between the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and their Mathematics teaching career.
3. Examine the relationship between Mathematics student teachers' self-efficacy and gender.

Research Questions

This research work was designed to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the mean score of the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics?
2. What is the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics teaching career?
3. Is there any difference in the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and gender?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were developed based on the research questions highlighted and tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

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- H₀₁: There is no significant relationship in the student-teachers' response between the sources of self-efficacy in Mathematics.
- H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between student-teachers' Mathematics self-efficacy and their career choices in Mathematics education.
- H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between student-teacher self-efficacy and gender differences.

Methodology

A correlational research design was adopted for the study because it focuses on the relationship between student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and the Mathematics teaching career. The population of the study consists of all level I00 (NCE I) student-teachers offering Mathematics as a teaching subject in Kano State's own colleges of education, a total of one hundred thirty-two (132) student-teachers as of the 2019/2020 academic session. All the population participate in the study. So, the sample size was one hundred thirty-two (132) Mathematics student-teachers, consisting of 75 males and 57 females. Census sampling technique was employed.

The instrument used for data collection was the Mathematics student-teacher self-efficacy scale (MSTSES). MSTSES was adapted from the work of Usher and Pajares (2009), validated by experts, where construct and face validity were emphasized in the validation assessment. The items were adjusted, and some were reconstructed based on the suggestions of the experts. The MSTSES was pilot tested for reliability purposes, and the internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha was found to be 0.84, which shows the MSTSES is valid and reliable.

The data collected were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation to answer the research question. The rule used to distinguish between an accepted and an unaccepted mean was the average of the four-point grading scale, which is 2.50. A mean score of 2.50 or higher is acceptable, while a score of less than 2.50 is not. While the hypotheses were tested using point-bi-serial and Pearson product moment correlation, SPSS software, version 22, was used for the analysis.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean score of the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics?

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**Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Student-teachers' Response on Self-efficacy.
 N=132**

Scales Items	Mean	SD	Decision
Mastery experience			
1 I make excellent grades on Mathematics tests.	1.57	0.65	Not Accepted
2 I have always been successful with Mathematics.	1.92	0.72	Not Accepted
3 Even when I study very hard, I perform poorly in Mathematics	1.59	0.83	Not Accepted
4 I got good grades in Mathematics on my last report card.	1.70	0.52	Not Accepted
5 I do well on math assignments.	1.57	0.65	Not Accepted
Vicarious Experience			
6 Seeing colloquies do well in Mathematics pushes me to do better.	1.76	0.72	Not Accepted
7 When I see how my Maths teacher solves a problem, I picture myself solving the problem in the same way.	1.84	0.73	Not Accepted
8 Seeing kids do better than me in Math encourage me to do better.	1.73	0.69	Not Accepted
9 When I see how another student solves a math problem, I can see myself solving the problem in the same way.	1.81	0.39	Not Accepted
10 I imagine myself working through challenging Maths problems successfully.	1.08	0.28	Not Accepted
Social Persuasion			
11 My math teachers have told that I am good at learning math.	1.41	0.55	Not Accepted
12 People have told me that I have a talent for math.	1.86	0.48	Not Accepted
13 Adults in my family have told me what a good math student I am.	1.43	0.55	Not Accepted
14 I have been praised for my ability in math.	1.65	0.63	Not Accepted
15 Other students have told me that I'm good at learning math.	1.59	0.68	Not Accepted
Physiological and Emotional State			
16 Just being in Maths class makes me feel stressed and nervous.	3.00	0.88	Accepted
17 Doing Maths work takes all of my energy.	1.16	0.44	Not Accepted
18 I start to feel stressed-out as soon as I begin my math work.	3.11	0.81	Accepted
19 My mind goes blank and I am unable to think clearly when doing Maths work.	2.35	0.85	Not Accepted
20 I get depressed when I think about learning Mathematics.	2.62	0.86	Accepted

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Table 1 shows the student-teacher’s responses to each of the four sources of self-efficacy in Mathematics. It is observed that the mean score of the responses in mastery experience, vicarious experience, and social experience is far below 2.50, and only in physiological and emotional state, the mean of three items accepted. This revealed that the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics is low.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship in the student-teachers’ response between the sources of self-efficacy in Mathematics.

Table 2: Point-Biserial Correlation of the Student-teachers Response between the Four Courses of Self-Efficacy. N=132

		Mastery Experience	Vicarious Experience	Social Persuasion	Physiological and Emotion State
Mastery Experience	r	1			
	Sig.				
Vicarious Experience	r	-.149	1		
	Sig.	.189			
Social Persuasion	r	.362*	-.348*	1	
	Sig.	.014	.017		
Physiological and Emotion State	r	.145	.293*	-.214	1
	Sig.	.196	.039	.101	

*significant correlation

The relationships between the student-teacher’s responses to the four sources of self-efficacy are shown in Table 2. The relationships between mastery and vicarious experiences is negative ($r(132)=-.149$; $\text{Sig}=.189$), indicating that $\text{Sig} > .05$; there is also no correlation between mastery and physiological or emotional state ($\text{Sig}=.196$), but there is a significant correlation between the student-teacher's response to mastery experience and social persuasion ($r = .362$; $\text{Sig}=.014$), indicating that $p < .05$. Another significant correlation is observed between vicarious experience and social persuasion ($r = -.348$; $\text{Sig}=.017$; and $r = -.293$; $\text{Sig} = .039$; respectively); this indicates that $P < .05$. Finally, there is no correlation between social persuasion and physiological or emotional state ($r = -.214$; $\text{Sig}=.101$), which implies that $\text{Sig} > .05$.

Research Question Two

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What is the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics teaching career?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of the Student-Teachers Mathematics Self-Efficacy and Teaching Career.

Career Choice	N	Student-teachers' Self-Efficacy		Mean Diff.	Remark
		Mean	SD		
Mathematics Teaching Career.	31	37.50	3.89	.30	Insignificance
Other Careers.	101	37.80	2.77		

Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics related to teaching career. According to the table, the number of student-teachers who chose Mathematics teaching as a career was thirty-one (31) with a mean of 37.50 with a standard deviation of 3.89. While one hundred and one (101) student-teachers with a mean of 37.80 and a 2.77 standard deviation reported that Mathematics teaching was not their career choice, a mean difference of 0.30 was found in favor of student-teachers who didn't choose Mathematics teaching as their career. However, the number of those whose Mathematics is not their career choice is larger than those who choose Mathematics teaching as their career.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between student-teachers' Mathematics self-efficacy and their career choices in Mathematics education.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation between Student-teachers Self-Efficacy and their Career Choice.

Student-teachers'	N	Mean	SD	r	Sig.	Decision
Self-Efficacy	132	37.50	3.89	.039	.409	Accept Hypothesis
Teaching Career	132	37.80	2.77			

Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC) in Table 4 revealed that there is no relationship between student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and their choice of teaching career ($r = .039$, $\text{Sig.} = .409$), which indicates that $\text{Sig.} > .05$. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, stated that there is no relationship between student teachers' self-efficacy and their career choice.

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Research Question Three

Is there any significant difference in the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and gender?

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of Student-teachers Self-Efficacy across Gender Differences.

Gender	N	Student-teachers Efficacy		Self-Mean Diff.	Decision
		Mean	SD		
Male	75	38.09	3.30	.78	Significance
Female	57	37.31	2.36		

Table 5 shows the mean and standard deviation of male and female student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics. A mean difference of 0.78 in favor of male student-teachers was recorded, and while the 2.36 standard deviation of the female student-teachers is less than that of the male 3.30, this shows there is a wide spread in the female responses.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant relationship between student-teacher self-efficacy and gender differences.

Table 6: Pearson Correlation between Male and Female Student-teachers' Self-Efficacy in Mathematics

Gender	N	r	Sig.
Male	75	.183	.249
Female	57		

Table 6 shows the correlation between the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics across gender differences. The table revealed that there is no significant relationship between male and female student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics ($r=.183$, $Sig = .249$).

Discussion of Findings

The present study contradicts the finding of Benaoui (2016); in this study, it is found that there is no correlation between mastery and vicarious experience, mastery

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experience and physiological and emotional state, and also social persuasion and physiological and emotional state. While Benaoui found that mastery experiences and physiological and emotional states are statistically correlated and influence students' performance, Benaoui also found that vicarious experiences and social persuasion are not significantly related. In this study, it is found that vicarious experiences and social persuasion are significantly related. Anyway, Benaoui in his study correlate the sources of the self-efficacy with the students' achievement in Mathematics.

In the present study, it is found that there are no relationships between student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and Mathematics teaching career; this contradicts the conclusion of Unsal et al. (2016), who found that Mathematics teachers have high self-efficacy levels. The contradiction might be because of the student-teachers are not service teachers, and they are newly admitted students, they are not exposed to teaching.

The present study also observed that there is no significant relationship between male and female student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics, which contradicts the finding of Ampofo (2019), who found no gender differences in student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics. The contradiction might be due to the small number of female student-teachers available for the present study.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that student-teachers have low self-efficacy in Mathematics. There is no relationship between the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and their choice of career. Finally, there is no relationship between student-teacher self-efficacy in Mathematics and gender.

Recommendations

1. The study recommends that students' self-efficacy in Mathematics and teaching Mathematics should be considered before they are admitted into any tertiary institution for education programs; this will help produce better future Mathematics teachers.
2. The study suggests that the government improve the welfare of the Mathematics teaching profession in order to pique the interest and attitude of student-teachers toward the profession.
3. Government, community, non-governmental organizations, and tertiary institution administrators should find a way to encourage females to pursue careers in Mathematics and to teach Mathematics.

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